

Data & results to generate figures in Zhu *et al.* 2026

Figure 1

GWAS summary statistics used to generate the Manhattan plots can be downloaded from the Neale Lab or from the source papers cited in the manuscript.

Approximately independent GWAS hits obtained from GCTA-COJO analysis:

1. [quant_hits.txt](#) file for quantitative traits

2. [disease_hits.txt](#) file for diseases

Figure 2

The list of quantitative traits and diseases can be found in Supplementary Table 1 and Supplementary tables 2-3, respectively.

Please compute S-LDSC p-values using your downloaded GWAS summary statistics, following the provided scripts for running S-LDSC.

3. [meta_analysis_neglog10p_matrix_ACAT.txt](#) file containing combined S-LDSC p-values for tissue enrichment, calculated using ACAT.

Figure 3

4. [gwas_zscore_deflation.txt](#) file containing the z-scores of significant hits from the original GWAS, along with the corresponding z-scores for these hits from GWAS of the binarized trait (left or right tail; 1%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 20% prevalence), and from GWAS of the downsampled trait (matched to 1%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 20% prevalence).

Figure 4

5. [inference_output.mat](#) file containing inference results, grouping traits as quantitative v. disease and brain-related v. non-brain-related. We report shared $f(s)$ distributions, along with heritability and mutational target size estimates. Results from 100 bootstrap replicates are included for confidence interval estimation.

Figure 5

6. [three_fs.mat](#) file containing the three $f(s)$ distributions shown in Figure 5D

7. simulations.zip folder containing simulations from (1) varying mutational target size, (2) varying $f(s)$, and (3) assuming no pleiotropy.

Figure 6

8. LoF_burden_tests_39new.zip folder containing LoF burden test summary statistics for the 39 quantitative traits not included in Milind *et al.*. For the remaining summary statistics, please download them from <https://zenodo.org/records/16800547>

Figure 7

9.gwas_prediction.mat file containing simulations for expected GWAS outcomes.

Supplementary figures

10. trait_specific_fs.mat file containing inferred trait-specific $f(s)$ for traits with more than 100 GWAS hits.